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1 Introduction: Project Title and Project Objectives

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01

TOPIC: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01

PROJECT: IMProving User experience, Long-term sustainability and Services of EU-OPENSREEN (IMPULSE). Website: <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/impulse/>. The INFRA-DEV project 'IMPULSE' is coordinated by EU-OPENSREEN ERIC and aims to expand EU-OPENSREEN's service offerings and scientific impact by integrating cutting-edge tools in AI/ML, novel chemical modalities, and advanced cell models, while standardising operations and enhancing outreach to foster reproducible, FAIR pre-clinical drug discovery.

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2 Policy Implications and Recommendations

2.1 Implementation of research infrastructures

New RI services in chemoproteomics and spatial MS-based omics

Building on the success of the Horizon 2020 INFRA-DEV project "EU-OPENSREEN-DRIVE" (Grant Agreement 823893) to develop a new concept for a new service to support users in the field of chemoproteomics and spatial MS-based omics, a transparent procedure for the provision of this new service has been launched. Chemoproteomics is an advanced set of techniques used to study interactions between small molecule drugs and proteins within complex biological systems. By combining chemical tools, high-throughput screening (HTS), mode-of-action (MoA) studies, and

cheminformatics, chemoproteomics enables researchers to map drug–target interactions across the entire proteome. This approach facilitates the discovery of novel drug candidates and uncovers new therapeutic pathways. Spatial MS-based omics, on the other hand, combines spatial data with omics analysis, allowing researchers to create detailed maps of biomolecule distributions in tissues and cells. Together, these methods provide powerful tools for studying molecular interactions in depth, advancing our understanding of complex biological systems and supporting the development of targeted therapies.

A transparent procedure for the selection of new EU-OPENSSCREEN partner sites providing chemoproteomics and spatial MS-based omics services was implemented, which included the evaluation of nominated sites by external experts in the field. This new type of RI service will be offered in future INFRA-SERV and other EU projects.

This example demonstrates the value of individual support actions for the evolution and long-term sustainability of individual pan-European RIs (INFRA-DEV). The European Commission should continue strengthening capacities of individual RIs/ERICs, including mature, time-tested RIs with proven track records in providing essential services to users, through these INFRA-DEV programmes.

2.2 International cooperation of research infrastructures

EU-OPENSSCREEN launched a federated repository of community compounds. This open compound sharing initiative bridges a critical gap between chemistry and biology by encouraging organic chemists and pharmacologists—often lacking platforms for broader biological testing—to share their compounds in a regulated and transparent framework. Besides engaging European chemists, EU-OPENSSCREEN also proactively reached out to international chemists in non-European countries (e.g., Australia, Brazil, Canada, Costa Rica, Chile, China, South Africa, South Korea, and Uruguay) to raise awareness about our compound sharing initiative and to encourage them to participate to attract RI users from overseas. Over the past 18 months, several non-European institutions signed a Material Transfer Agreement (MTA) with EU-OPENSSCREEN and shared compounds: Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Universidad de Valparaíso in Chile, Universidad de Costa Rica, Curtin University in Perth, Western Australia, Queensland University in Brisbane, Australia, and the Chinese Academic of Medical Science and Peking Union Medical College. Besides chemistry users, EU-OPENSSCREEN attracted biologists from South Africa and Brazil to access EU-OPENSSCREEN for their discovery projects.

IMPULSE partners organised training activities specifically targeting the international scientific community, including the following training courses:

- Training course “Integrative Structural Biology meets Drug Discovery Workshop”, co-organised by EU-OPENSSCREEN, the Brazilian Center for Research in Energy and Materials (CNPEM), Instruct-ERIC and CEBEM (<https://pages.cnpem.br/isbdd/>).
- “Assay Guidance Workshop for High-Throughput Screening and Lead Discovery”, co-organised by the NIH NCATS, EU-OPENSSCREEN, EATRIS and Nuvisan (<https://ncats.corsizio.com/event/66f2d5e6960282a2f3620b4d>). The workshop, originally planned for 2025, was indefinitely postponed by the NIH.
- “Comprehensive Workshop on Preclinical Drug Discovery (CDD)”, co-organised by the H3D-University of Cape Town in South Africa, and the IMPULSE partners EU-OPENSSCREEN and Fraunhofer ITMP (<https://h3dfoundation.org/reflections-on-our-comprehensive-workshop-on-preclinical-drug-discovery-cdd/>).

EU-OPENSSCREEN successfully applied for funding under HORIZON-INFRA-2024-DEV-01-02 and is coordinating the RAFIKI project (<https://rafiki-project.eu/>, Grant Agreement 101188390) with partners in Europe and across sub-Saharan Africa. RAFIKI aims to strengthen capacity for drug

discovery and development across sub-Saharan Africa and to foster cooperation between African and European researchers.

The Commission should continue to foster alignment with international peers, especially in data harmonisation and AI standards, international training programmes and facilitation of access to RIs by international users, to support global collaboration and European competitiveness.

2.3 Employment and skills in research infrastructures

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) have rapidly become transformative tools in early drug discovery, reshaping how small molecules are prioritised, designed, and optimised. Training programmes in AI for the life sciences should be prioritised, especially at the interface of chemical biology, data science, and pharmacology, to support the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers. Initial versions of these courses are currently being developed in the frame of the EU-OPENSSCREEN core funding and IMPULSE project (<https://web.unica.it/unica/protected/496793/0/def/ref/AVS496791/>).

2.4 Interaction of research infrastructures with industry

IMPULSE has delivered tangible results in fostering public–private collaboration:

- One-on-one interviews with Industry Liaison Office (ILO) representatives enabled identifying industry needs. The results are incorporated in the Catalogue of Expertise of EU-OPENSSCREEN (see D8.1). This expertise is being used i) to generate seven co-development projects for EU-OPENSSCREEN partners with pharmaceutical and biotech companies (see M8.1); and ii) to create focus groups on topics of interest (targeted protein degraders, stabilised mutant proteins, etc.).
- The possibility of applying as a consortium to different national and European calls for projects. The ILO representatives of AstraZeneca, GSK, and Lilly are exploring common opportunities with various EU-OPENSSCREEN partners.
- Efficient models of public–private partnership/commitment letter agreements to initiate collaborations exploring programmes that will be tailored towards comprehensive agreements.

The impact of these collaborations is expected to contribute to the growth of regional innovation ecosystems. To maintain this momentum, we recommend strengthening the role of the ILO, expanding co-development opportunities, and ensuring flexible and industry-friendly access policies.

2.5 Technology development, data and digital services, digitalisation

Incorporating AI and ML into early-stage compound screening and pharmacological profiling

Within the IMPULSE framework, EU-OPENSSCREEN is developing AI-based services to support the deconvolution of compound modes of action, an essential component of the hit-to-lead optimisation process. IMPULSE marks a substantial European effort to modernise drug discovery research infrastructures by incorporating AI and ML into early-stage compound screening and pharmacological profiling.

The outcomes of IMPULSE directly support several European Union policy objectives. In terms of strategic autonomy in health, the integration of AI services into EU-OPENSSCREEN reduces European dependency on external discovery pipelines and strengthens the capacity of internal R&I systems. IMPULSE also aligns with the European Commission's Digital Europe strategy by embedding AI tools into accessible infrastructures, enabling researchers to apply these methods without deep technical expertise.

To maximise the long-term benefit of initiatives such as IMPULSE, we recommend that the European Commission works to establish a clear regulatory and ethical framework to guide AI/ML applications in preclinical research, a topic where EU-OPENSREEN is currently creating a new consortium to address this question directly. EU-OPENSREEN looks forward to helping develop such a framework to ensure privacy and quality control while promoting innovation and cross-border collaboration.

2.6 Level of connection of RI to EOSC

IMPULSE supports EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) ambitions through its contributions to data standardisation, interoperability, and the adoption of ontologies such as the BioAssay Ontology (BAO). The connection with the recently finalised EOSC-Life, BY-COVID, EOSC4Cancer, and FAIRplus initiatives demonstrates a clear and practical alignment with open science goals.

